

Supplemental Data

Figure 1: Compared to their wild-type (WT) counterparts, humanized *BRCA1* female and male mice differ in total food consumed, number of feeding bouts, and quantity of water consumed. **Panel A:** Total Food During Cycle (g) over a 24-hour period in WT (n=10, solid blue bars) and humanized *BRCA1* females (n=10, hashed blue bars) at 6 months and 1 year of age ($p = 2.3e-9$ and $p = 0.053$, respectively); **Panel B:** Total Food During Cycle (g) over a 24-hour period in WT (n=10, solid green bars) and humanized *BRCA1* males (n=17, hashed green bars) at 6 months and 1 year of age ($p = 0.002856$ and $p = 0.078$, respectively); **Panel C:** Number of feeding bouts over a 24-hour period in WT and humanized *BRCA1* females at 6 months and 1 year of age ($p = 0.012$ and $p = 0.137$, respectively); **Panel D:** Number of feeding bouts over a 24-hour period in WT and humanized *BRCA1* males at 6 months and 1 year of age ($p = 6.34e-5$ and $p = 0.003$, respectively); **Panel E:** Total Water During Cycle (g) over a 24-hour period in WT and humanized *BRCA1* females at 6 months and 1 year of age ($p = 0.0002$ and $p = 5.21e-5$, respectively); **Panel F:** Total Water During Cycle (g) over a 24-hour period in WT and humanized *BRCA1* males at 6 months and 1 year of age ($p = 5.8e-14$ and $p = 0.78$, respectively). *Denotes a statistically significant difference between groups of same gender and age.

Figure 2: Wild-type (WT) and humanized *BRCA1* female mice display a variation in respiratory quotient at 6 months during the daytime while WT and humanized *BRCA1* male mice display a variation in respiratory quotient at 6 and 12 months of age, both during the day and night. **Panel A:** Average respiratory quotient during 12-hour periods in WT (n=10, closed black circles) and humanized *BRCA1* females (n=10, closed red circles) at 6 months and 1 year of age ($p = 0.047$ for 6 months day; solid lines, $p = 0.49$ for 6 months night; dashed lines; and $p = 0.24$ for 12 months day and $p = 0.11$ for 12 months night, respectively); **Panel B:** Average respiratory quotient during 12-hour periods in WT (n=10, black triangles) and humanized (n=17, blue triangles) males at 6 months and 1 year of age ($p = 0.002$ for 6 months day; solid lines, $p = 0.032$ for 6 months night; dashed lines; and $p = 0.03$ for 12 months day and $p = 0.008$ for 12 months night, respectively). *Denotes a statistically significant difference between groups of same gender and age.

Figure 3: Wild-type (WT) and humanized *BRCA1* female and male mice differ in resting energy expenditure at 6 months and 1 year of age and this difference is noticed both during the day and during the night. Humanized *BRCA1* females also have higher Ped Meters during the night at 12 months while humanized *BRCA1* male mice have higher Ped Meters at both time points during the day and night. **Panel A:** Resting Energy Expenditure (kcal/hr) in WT (solid blue bars) and humanized *BRCA1* females (hashed blue bars) at 6 months and 1 year of age ($p = 0.0008$ and $p = 6.1e-5$, respectively); **Panel B:** Resting Energy Expenditure (kcal/hr) in WT (solid green bars) and humanized *BRCA1* males (hashed green bars) at 6 months and 1 year of age ($p = 0.008$ and $p = 4.9e-7$, respectively); **Panel C:** Average energy expenditure during 12-hour periods in WT (black circles) and humanized *BRCA1* females (red circles) at 6 months and 1 year of age ($p = 0.0024$ for 6 months day (solid lines), $p = 7.9e-10$ for 6 months night (dashed lines), $p = 2.06e-6$ for 12 months day, and $p = 2.85e-9$ for 12 months night, respectively); **Panel D:** Average energy expenditure during 12-hour periods in WT (black triangles) and humanized *BRCA1* males (blue triangles) at 6 months and 1 year of age ($p = 8.2e-4$ for 6 months day (solid lines), $p = 2.3e-12$ for 6 months night (dashed lines), $p = 2.4e-4$ for 12 months day, and $p = 6.9e-8$ for 12 months night, respectively); **Panel E:** Ped Meters during 12-hour periods in WT and humanized *BRCA1* females at 6 months and 1 year of age ($p = 0.877$ for 6 months day, $p = 0.485$ for 6 months night; and $p = 0.13$ for 12 months day and $p = 0.012$ for 12 months night, respectively); **Panel F:** Ped Meters during 12-hour periods in WT and humanized *BRCA1* males

at 6 months and 1 year of age ($p = 5.40e-7$ for 6 months day, $p = 1.15e-14$ for 6 months night; and $p = 0.0115$ for 12 months day and $p = 6.02e-9$ for 12 months night, respectively). *Denotes a statistically significant difference between groups of same gender and age.

Table 1: Humanized *BRCA1* females have altered expression in multiple genes related to glucose metabolism as compared to their wild-type counterparts.